

Elene Khachapuridze

Akaki Tchkhenskeli and the Committee for Assisting Georgian Tuberculosis
Patients in Paris

Saint Andrew the First-Called Georgian University

School of Humanities and Law – Department of History

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"The rights of Georgia are undeniable, yet just as rights can be gained, they can also be lost. Rights must be defended. If violated, they must be restored."¹ - These words, spoken by Giorgi Gvazava, were published in *Independent Georgia* in 1926. Just five years had passed since the Sovietization of Georgia, and our government, now in exile, was striving to restore Georgia's violated rights.

In March 1921, Grigol Lortkipanidze and Mamia Orkhelashvili signed a treaty halting military operations, but this did not mean that Georgia recognized Bolshevik rule. The government did not resign but managed to flee into exile. Concerning this, *Independent Georgia* published in its February 1926 issue: "When Lenin was informed about the Red Army's entry into Georgia and the emigration of Noe Zhordania's government, it is said that Pugachev's grandson remarked to him: 'So, you couldn't take Georgia after all!'" Though this may be a historical anecdote, such stories are valuable as they often reflect the spirit of their time.²

Akaki Tchkhenskeli was one of those patriots who, while striving to restore our country's violated rights, also assisted Georgians living in exile. Tchkhenskeli's political, scientific, and cultural contributions in emigration, and his service to Georgians and to Georgia, have yet to be fully studied.

He was born in 1874 in the village of Okumi, Sukhumi district, to a family of five children. He studied at the Khoni school before enrolling in the Tbilisi Theological Seminary, from which he was expelled in 1893 due to his participation in a "general strike." Between 1896 and 1901, he studied law at the universities of Kyiv, Moscow, and Saint Petersburg. From 1902 to 1904, he worked as a lawyer in the Sukhumi district and contributed articles to both Russian and Georgian press. His writings appeared under various pseudonyms: *Anchini*, *P. Okumeli*, *Tsintsqali*, and others. Due to his opposition to Russia's anti-Georgian policies, he was exiled from the Caucasus.

From 1905 to 1910, Tchkhenskeli studied workers' movements and national issues in Europe, attended conferences- - all to further his intellectual development. He graduated from Leipzig University in 1907 and pursued further studies in Geneva. Upon his return to Georgia in 1909, he became involved in publishing the works of the Social Democratic Party. However, in 1910, he was imprisoned in Metekhi Fortress and later exiled to Rostov-on-Don, though he managed to escape and return to Georgia. In 1912, he defended the rights of Georgians, and in 1916, he advocated for the rights of the Adjarians.

In 1917, following the February Revolution in Russia, the Provisional Government appointed Akaki Tchkhenskeli as a member of the Special Transcaucasian Committee

¹ Gvazava, G. (1926, January). *Independent Georgia*, 2.

² Amirejibi, Sh. (1926, February). *After February 25. Independent Georgia*, 1.

(OZAKOM). In April, he was elected chairman of the Interparty Council. On February 8, 1918, he presided over the opening of Tbilisi State University. That same month, he became a member of both the Transcaucasian Sejm and Commissariat and led the delegation to the Trebizond Conference. On May 26, 1918, he was appointed as the Minister of Foreign Affairs. Following the elections of March 1919, he became a member of the Constituent Assembly.³

Here, we shall not focus on his activities in Georgia, but rather on his role in emigration, beginning in January 1921.

Before the Soviet annexation, Akaki Tchkhenskeli was dispatched as Georgia's ambassador to France. Even after the Soviet occupation, he continued his diplomatic efforts in Paris as head of the Georgian Legation. In early 1921, Tchkhenskeli was appointed Georgia's plenipotentiary representative not only in Paris but also in Rome, London, and various Western European countries.

In April 1922, he led the Georgian delegation at the Genoa Conference and continued his diplomatic work in Paris until 1934, when the French-Soviet pact led to the revocation of the Georgian Democratic Republic's embassy status.

Life for Georgian émigrés in France was far from ideal. Although the January 24, 1926 issue of the newspaper *Communist* claimed that "the upper echelons of the émigrés are living comfortably, sustained by the sale of jewelry (part of which E. Takaishvili was forced to bring from the treasury and sell)," the reality was quite different. *Independent Georgia* responded to this by stating that such claims were entirely baseless.

In fact, the majority of Georgian emigres endured dire conditions, made worse by the rampant spread of tuberculosis. Newspapers regularly published obituaries, listing names such as Misha Kakhiashvili, Kukuri Kekelidze, artist Shalva Kikodze, and officer Giotto Emukhvari. The reports stated: "Many are ill, and a special organization is needed to care for them."⁴

At the initiative of Akaki Tchkhenskeli, on March 3, 1929, the "Committee for Assisting Georgian Tuberculosis Patients" was established. It should be noted that this charitable organization was preceded by a similar initiative, the "Georgian Doctors' Association," founded a few years earlier. Information about this organization appeared in the March 1926 issue of *Independent Georgia*. The association had 15 members, including Chairman V. Ghambashidze and Secretary A. Zhorzholiani, whose mission was to provide medical assistance to Georgians in Paris.

³ (Daushvili, 2007)

⁴ (Daushvili, 2007, p. 133)

The growing number of tuberculosis-related deaths, the unbearable living conditions, and the lack of support led Akaki Tchkhenskeli to create the Committee. This initiative was strongly supported by Inna Zhordania. A call was published in *Independent Georgia*, urging Georgians to join the organization and contribute to saving their compatriots. The call highlighted the grim situation that had brought the émigrés to such a desperate state: "This has happened because these unfortunate individuals, weakened by hard labor or lack of nutrition, could not withstand the illness, which requires special care, treatment, and proper conditions to fight."

Akaki Tchkhenskeli was elected honorary chairman of the Committee, with Elene Abkhazi serving as chairperson. Significant contributions to the Committee's activities were also made by Anton Zhorzholiani and Davit Skhirtladze. The Committee's statutes were drafted by Davit Sharashidze, although these documents remain unavailable for the present study.⁵

The Committee began its work without initial funds and had to seek resources externally. They could not maintain their own sanatorium, let alone provide aid to the sick. The solution was found in organizing charitable events. The first such event of the season was held in October 1929. Through this evening's efforts, Georgian expatriates in Harbin made financial contributions to the Committee. It was then decided that donations could be collected not only in France but elsewhere, although the Committee's primary responsibility remained focused on Georgians residing in Paris.

Independent Georgia regularly published reports detailing the funding sources for the Committee. The former government of Georgia donated 3,500 francs. Donations also came from Georgians living in Odenkirchen, Harbin, Persia, Warsaw, and Prague.

To organize charitable events, the Committee collaborated with various other organizations, including the "Committee for Assisting Georgia" and the "Society of Friends of Georgia".

In April 1934, the hundredth issue of *Independent Georgia* featured an appeal to Georgians in exile, describing the immense hardships faced by the Georgian community abroad. It spoke of moral depression, increasing mortality, and the prevalence of various diseases. The article stated: "To this day, the Society for Assisting Tuberculosis Patients has been tirelessly caring for the seriously ill."

To further their work, the Committee members decided to establish a separate section called the "Youth Aid Organization," aimed at providing both moral and material support to young people.

⁵ (Daushvili, 2007, p. 133)

Despite financial support from various organizations, material assistance was still insufficient, and there was an urgent need for broader public support in the form of money, food, and clothing.

“By the end of 1937, new members were elected to the Committee's board, including S. Tsitsishvili, N. Imnaishvili, N. Zurabishvili, E. Pataridze, V. Faghava, T. Japaridze, and A. Gedevanishvili, who enthusiastically engaged in the organization's activities. It was decided to introduce shifts at the refugee office to provide the sick with necessary information regarding doctors and hospitals. The Committee also collected second-hand clothing, shoes, and underwear, as there were often no resources to purchase these items. The Committee supported 40 patients in various categories, covering their treatment in sanatoriums, hospitals, or at home; it provided medicine, food, financial assistance, and most importantly, moral support. Less affluent Georgians helped by contributing food, medication, or their labor.”⁶

Thus, Akaki Tchkhenskeli's significant initiative greatly aided the government and people in exile who tirelessly sought to restore Georgia's violated rights, struggled for survival, and aimed to instill the spirit of resistance in future generations. The Committee saved many lives and provided hope to those suffering from material depression.

Akaki Tchkhenskeli passed away in 1959 and is buried in the Georgian cemetery in Leuville.

Bibliography:

1. *After February 25th*. (1926, No. 2). *Independent Georgia*, pp. 1, 4.
2. Avalishvili, L., Kldiashvili, G., & Kalandadze, E. (2022). *Akaki Tchkhenskeli*. Tbilisi: IDFI; TSU; NPLG.
3. Amirejibi, Sh. (February 1926). *After February 25th*. *Independent Georgia*, p. 1.
4. Gvazava, G. (January 1926). *Independent Georgia*, p. 2.
5. Daushvili, R. (2007). *Georgian Emigration in 1921-1939*. RAE.
6. *Appeal*. (1934, No. 100). *Independent Georgia*, pp. 15-16.
7. *Appeal of the Committee for Assisting Tuberculosis Patients*. (1929, No. 39). *Independent Georgia*, p. 15.
8. *Report and Account of the Committee for Assisting Tuberculosis Patients*. (1931, No. 62). *Independent Georgia*, p. 16.
9. Zhordania, I. (1930, No. 7). *Committee for Assisting Tuberculosis Patients*. *Independent Georgia*, p. 4.

⁶ (Daushvili, 2007)

10. *Georgian Doctors' Association*. (1926, No. 3). *Independent Georgia*, p. 4.
11. *Georgians in France*. (1930, No. 59). *Independent Georgia*, p. 10.
12. *Georgian Evening*. (1929, No. 46). *Independent Georgia*, p. 10.
13. *Annual Report of the Committee for Assisting Georgian Tuberculosis Patients*. (1930, No. 52). *Independent Georgia*, pp. 13-15.